

CA20104 – Network on evidence-based physical activity in old age (PhysAgeNet)

Deliverable D1.1

D1.1 Database with references and metadata related to PA interventions and based on EBM. (Collection update after two years), Complete coverage of EU funded research. Updated versions of the reference database include evaluation results (one category or target groups per year with evidence level and generalisation options)

RCO 4 Compile a database of literature references involving technology-assisted PA interventions, utilizing evidence levels and reach/generalisation according to EBM standards.

Contributors

Working Group 1

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1. RESULTS

Deliverable 1.1. is due September 2023 – 100% achieved

In the following we will give a short description on what has been done to achieve D1.1: Reviewing the EBM concepts and material for examining the usefulness of these concepts for PhysAgeNet´s topics. Compiling a toolbox with EBM guidelines, checklists, and frameworks which may be applied directly or need to be modified for use in the area of PA in old age

1. EBM concepts and guidelines have been reviewed

To account for EBM criteria within systematic reviews, the GRADE system was applied as a mandatory part of the systematic reviews in all working groups. The specific requirements of the GRADE system were summarized within a manual that can be used within the whole COST action. Moreover, we conducted a training school at Kaunas and an additional workshop on how to use the GRADE system and on the theoretical background. These presentation slides are also accessible for COST action member

2. A toolbox of guidelines to conduct systematic reviews to compile a data of literature has been developed

To secure standard of exercise reporting and EBM guidelines, exercise interventions need to follow the F.I.T.T principles (frequency, intensity, type, time, ASCM, 2017). Moreover, evidence-based training principles like individualisation, specificity or progression should be considered as they contribute to health- related positive adaption of exercise.

Studies included in systematic reviews and the database of literature should report on these aspects. As the research field of providing physical activity and exercise interventions for older adults is broad, including many disciplines, these aspects are often not reported in the existing body of literature.

Therefore, we developed guidelines to conduct systematic reviews. Further we conducted a Delphi-process across all PhysAgeNet members on the categorization of exercise intensities. Within this process we were able to gain an overall agreement on how to determine and describe exercise intensities of different types of exercise if the information is not provided in the included studies of a systematic review. This information was shared with the whole COST action afterwards. Moreover, the scientific manuscript is actually under revision at the Journal: European Review of Aging and Physical activity.

3. The final toolbox will be developed until March 2024 (see D1.3)..

American College of Sports Medicine. ACSM's Guidelines for Exercise Testing and Prescription, 10th ed.; Wolters Kluwer: Alphen aan den Rijn, The Netherlands (2017). ISBN 9788578110796

In the following you will find the links to (1) the database, (2) EU funded research, and (3) EBM guidelines:

1. Links to data bases

executive functions: [articles executive function.ris](#)
depression: [articles#1_depression.ris](#) [articles#2_depression.ris](#)
quality of life: [Quality_of_Life_Articles_Included_Lamberti.xlsx](#)

2. Link to EU funded research:

[Healthy_Ageing_funded_EU_projects.pdf](#)

3. Link to EBM guidelines and related materials

Link to presentation on systematic review: [PP_Systematic_Review_COST_revised_MF \[SchreibgeschÃ¼tzt\].pdf](#)

Link to GRADE presentation: [GRADE - Grading the quality and strength of evidence_Giorgios Sakkas.pdf](#)

Link to GRADE manual: [Guidance to integrate GRADE \(2\).docx](#)

Link to Intensity recommendations: [FITT criteria for training description_WP1_20220928.pdf](#) [Delphi_RESULTS_Stage3_for WGs.docx](#)